

Original Research Article

Whose Classroom is it? Language and Cultural Representation in Digital Learning Videos Across State, National, and Global Platforms

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ABSTRACT

Digital learning videos have become an increasingly prominent component of secondary education worldwide, particularly following the COVID-19 pandemic. While digitalisation and its resources are often assessed in terms of accessibility, engagement, or learning outcomes; their role as media texts that construct language, culture, and learner identity remains under explored, so this study tries to explore digital learning videos as sites of representation and also examines how educational media produced at different levels of platform governance shape the imagined classroom specifically in secondary education. Adopting a qualitative content analysis, this study compares ten publicly accessible secondary level instructional videos drawn from three platforms: a state-level initiative, a national platform and a global platform. Videos spanning both STEM and non-STEM subjects were thus analysed using a thematic coding framework focusing on language of instruction, cultural specificity, bit of visual pedagogy, and also learner identity construction, localisation, and governance orientation. The study identifies a clear representational shift: state-level videos emphasise linguistic accessibility and local cultural relevance, national-level content prioritises standardisation, and global platforms favour culturally abstract, English-dominant, scalable instruction. These patterns suggest that educational media are not neutral tools but institutionally shaped artefacts that may inadvertently reproduce existing inequalities by privileging dominant epistemologies.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received on

30 December 2025

Accepted on

02 March 2026

Published on

30 June 2026

KEYWORDS

Digital learning video; Educational media; Localisation; Platform governance; Representation

Vol. 01, No. 01, pp. 35-56

REPRESENT URL

<https://represent.co.in/index.php/rep/article/view/1.1.3>

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21080094>

Introduction

Education is not merely transmission of knowledge but also a social process through which values, identities, and world views are shaped. Schools play a function as critical social institutions where young people encounter academic content and implicit ideas about language, culture, authority, and belongingness. Among all the stages of formal schooling, secondary education is a phase where learners begin to engage with abstract thinking, disciplinary knowledge, and social identities in a more complex way. While simultaneously negotiating

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questions of selfhood, aspiration, and social location (UNESCO, 2017), learners consider education a public good and a collective social responsibility rather than a commodity. Schooling plays a crucial role in the social reproduction of knowledge, language, and cultural capital, shaping how young people are positioned within broader social hierarchies (Apple, 2004; Giroux, 2011), especially in secondary education which is considered from class VI to Class X in India. Within this framework, digital educational resources cannot be treated as neutral technological interventions, rather are embedded within political economies of education reflecting and often reinforcing existing inequalities. Hence decisions regarding language of instruction, cultural context, and pedagogical design in digital learning videos may carry ideological weight, determining whose knowledge is legitimised and whose experiences are marginalised.

As digital platforms increasingly mediate access to secondary education, across state, national, and global levels, it becomes imperative to critically examine whether these technologies democratise education or subtly reconfigure educational inequities under the guise of accessibility and innovation. With growing reliance on global digital platforms, concerns about the privatisation and platformisation of pedagogical authority, where curriculum design, representational choices, and learner engagement are increasingly shaped by institutional logics external to local educational communities, have been raised (Selwyn, 2016; Williamson & Hogan, 2020). Even non-profit platforms, operating within global digital economies, may privilege standardisation and scale over linguistic plurality and cultural specificity, thereby reproducing asymmetries between the global north and the global south (Selwyn, 2016).

From a global perspective, secondary education has undergone substantial transformation over the last two decades which can be observed across countries as there has been a steady move toward curriculum standardisation, competency-based learning, and the integration of digital technologies into classroom instruction (OECD, 2020, March 20). There are persistent inequalities within secondary education systems linking language, region, class, gender, and also access to digital media resources which in fact shapes how a learner can experience schooling (Selwyn, 2016), and in India, secondary education hence, carries additional layers of complexity (UNESCO, 2017), as it operates within a diverse linguistically and culturally diverse society where schooling is mediated by different educational boards, curricula, and linguistic regimes. Thus, policy frameworks such as the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasises on inclusion, multilingualism, and technology integration, the lived realities of classrooms often reflect uneven access to quality resources and digital infrastructure (Ministry of Education, 2020), and hence factors like regional disparities, or language hierarchies, or

maybe even socio economic differences do continue to influence how students engage with educational content particularly at the secondary level where academic pressure intensifies for them with board examinations.

Accelerated by the COVID 19 pandemic, digital videos have become a routine component of secondary education, supplementing textbooks and classroom teaching across state, national, and global platforms (OECD, 2020, March 20). Further, government initiatives such as state education portals, national platforms like Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing (DIKSHA), and global platforms such as Khan Academy now coexist within students' learning ecosystems, often accessed interchangeably by teachers and learners. While digital learning videos are frequently evaluated in terms of effectiveness, engagement, or learning outcomes, comparatively less attention has been paid to their role as media representations.

Educational videos are not neutral pedagogical tools; they are media texts that encode particular assumptions about who the learner is, what language counts as legitimate knowledge, and which cultural contexts are made visible or invisible (Buckingham, 2003). Use of language, examples, visuals, narration style, and instructional design, help construct an "imagined classroom" and an "imagined learner" that reflect broader institutional and ideological priorities. This becomes significant when educational videos operate at different levels of governance with state level initiatives often emphasising on regional language and curricular alignment; while national platforms prioritise standardisation and scalability; global platforms focus on universality and abstraction (Selwyn, 2016). Hence, carrying implications for language accessibility, cultural specificity, and learner identity, particularly in diverse and multilingual countries such as India (Chowdhury et al., 2011).

Conversely, locally produced content may enhance familiarity and inclusion, but it remains limited in interactivity or technological sophistication (Pym, 2010). Hence, study of these negotiations and resistances within secondary education videos is therefore critical for evaluating their broader social and pedagogical implications (Karimov et al., 2024) to highlight how globally produced educational videos benefit from polished visuals and scalable design, thereby erasing the localized cultural and linguistic contexts.

Using qualitative content analysis of select secondary level educational videos from state, national and global platforms, this study explores how different platform governance and their frameworks shape different representational choices in digital classrooms. Consequently, this paper also locates various nuances of educational media, not just the instructional element, but as sites of representation where various language, culture, pedagogy, and power intersect with

each other. Rather than offering a comprehensive evaluation or ranking, the paper adopts an exploratory perspective, mapping patterns and contrasts in how learners and learning environments are imagined across platforms. Further, this study deconstructs how such portrayals within social institutions contributes to ongoing discussions on education, media, and social justice. By emphasising with representation in digital education, the paper tries to reflect on a central question: whose language, whose culture, and whose classroom are being represented in the rapidly expanding digital landscape of secondary education?

Review of Literature

Media and education scholars argue that educational media are not neutral conveyers of content but pedagogical actors that construct an “imagined learner” (Buckingham, 2003) and this positioning shapes explicit expectations about prior knowledge, language competence, and cultural capital while implicitly assigns social identity markers (class, region, gender) to the prototypical student. Studies on media pedagogy emphasise that digital formats (video plus platform) alter the teacher student relationship and the symbolic infrastructure of schooling, shifting authority from local institutions to platform logics and standardised curricula (Buckingham, 2003; Selwyn, 2016). These arguments are essential when comparing state (regionally situated) and global (platform driven) educational content (Buckingham, 2003; Selwyn, 2016). Content analysis research in media studies demonstrate persistent patterns of inclusion or exclusion in mediated texts based on gender and ethnic stereotyping, uneven visibility of minority groups, and dominant cultural framings (Chitra & Senthilkumar, 2023; Yadav, 2024) and when applied to educational media, these patterns imply that seemingly neutral examples (names, contexts, images) operate as representational cues that either broaden or narrow learners’ sense of belonging.

Representation in language and media have theoretical foundations with the study of educational videos as cultural artefacts must begin with an account of meaning making practices, as Stuart Hall’s (1997) foundational work argues that representation is an active process of producing meaning where media texts encode and circulate ideologies about identities, social roles and power relations. Further, Fairclough (1995) and van Dijk (1993) provide analytic tools such as critical discourse analysis to identify these representational codes of power relations and dominations. Critical linguistics interrogates how language constructs social actors reproducing hierarchies through seemingly neutral pedagogical discourse. Together these theoretical resources provide the conceptual backbone for analysing how digital learning videos position languages (regional, national, global) and represent learners’ social

identities within mediated classrooms (Hall, 1997; Fairclough, 1995; van Dijk, 1993). Studies in childhood media representation and educational imagery find that consciously inclusive design (diverse names, multilingual captions, varied settings) improves learners' identification and can counteract marginalising school cultures (Chitra & Senthilkumar, 2023).

Studies on Khan Academy, a paradigmatic global video platform, indicate that its short, visual tutorials combined with online practice support learning gains when embedded in a supportive school ecosystem accompanied by teacher facilitation (Murphy et al., 2014; Bergstrom & Yamkovenko, 2025, March 20). However, several independent evaluations including randomised and quasi experimental studies in diverse contexts show mixed results depending on implementation quality, teacher coaching, and language accessibility (de Moura Caria et al., 2017; Bergstrom & Yamkovenko, 2025, March 20; Murphy et al., 2014). Further, studies focusing on localisation, through translation and cultural adaptation, show an increase in uptake and comprehension among non-English speakers, although full curricular alignment and cultural contextualisation remain a challenge (Karimov et al., 2024).

DIKSHA, an Indian platform which follows National Council of Educational Research and Training or NCERT ecosystem, is an instructive case of national level digitisation that aims to balance standardisation and state diversity. Studies reflect that although DIKSHA supports multilingual state level content but fall short on maintain even quality, accessibility gaps, and a tendency toward curricular standardisation limiting the regional flavour (Sharma, 2021). Research on DIKSHA's rollout during COVID 19 documented rapid scaling but variable teacher readiness and infrastructural constraints, especially in rural context (Azim Premji Foundation, 2021). NCERT technical briefs and evaluations of DIKSHA content quality and teacher perceptions find generally positive attitudes but highlight needs for richer localisation and pedagogical scaffolding (teacher training, in video formative checks) to make content more inclusive that are recent empirical studies and institutional evaluations (Karwal, 2021).

Localisation (making content linguistically and culturally relevant) and internationalisation (designing content for broad, cross-cultural use) are central concerns for digital learning resources. Empirical studies show localisation as something more than translation, as it requires adaptation of metaphors, examples, imagery, and pedagogical scaffolds to be culturally meaningful (Chowdhury et al., 2011; Esselink, 2000). Researchers find that well executed localisation increases comprehension and learner engagement, especially in multilingual contexts; conversely, poor localisation often reproduces cultural distance and epistemic exclusion (Chowdhury et al., 2011; Pym, 2010). Further, in large open platforms, tradeoffs

between scalability and situated-ness are persistent; projects that attempt community driven localisation (volunteer translators, teacher networks) report promising gains but require governance and quality control (Karimov et al., 2024). State level channels which typically follows State Council of Educational Research and Training or SCERT produced videos (e.g., West Bengal's Banglar Shiksha Online) illustrate a contrasting representational logic: lessons delivered in the regional language and packaged with locally salient metaphors and cultural references, and localisation at the state level enhances linguistic accessibility and cultural belonging, but studies caution that regional content can also reproduce dominant regional norms (urban bias, standard dialect) while marginalising sub regional, tribal, or minority voices (Chowdhury et al., 2011).

Language policy and education literature in India provide important background for interpreting digital content where NEP 2020 emphasises multilingual education (Ministry of Education, 2020). Instruction in mother tongue is introduced in early years of a child's education, but implementation at the secondary level remains complex (Ministry of Education, 2020) aiding comprehension and conceptual learning, while English-only instruction can operate as a barrier for many students. These help identify how state (regional language) vs national (Hindi/English) vs global (English) video content differentially position learners. Digital divide highlights that access, device ownership, and digital literacy shape who benefits from online educational videos (Selwyn, 2016) where accessibility of DIKSHA and other portals also reveal varying support for learners with disabilities, and inconsistent availability of subtitles or transcripts and low bandwidth options (Karwal, 2021; Sharma, 2021). Platform governance including moderation, translation, and teacher support emphasise that platform features such as practice problems, auto grading, analytics are meaningful only when matched with equitable access and contextualised pedagogy (Sharma, 2021).

A recurring theme emerging out of the existing literature is the conflict between scalability and situated-ness where global platforms achieve scale (and technical polish) but risk erasing cultural specificity, state platforms foreground local language and identity but may lack advanced interactivity and global content quality, and national platforms attempt a middle path yet face governance complexity and uneven localisation (Chowdhury et al., 2011; Murphy et al., 2014; Sharma, 2021). Importantly for the present paper, the literature shows that representational choices in video text (language, examples, visual design) materially shape learner identity. This paper, hence, tries to fill up the gap of lack of adequate studies adopting rigorous comparative content analysis across governance levels and systematic studies of how localisation choices affect learners' sense of cultural inclusion in secondary schooling contexts.

Research Questions

These questions integrate concerns about language, culture, learner identity, and governance level into a unified analytical focus for the content analysis. This study will be guided by the following research questions:

1. How are language and cultural contexts represented in digital learning videos across state, national, and global platforms, and what learner identities and cultural perspectives are constructed through these representations?
2. How do different levels of educational governance (state, national, global) influence the degree of localisation, cultural specificity, and linguistic accessibility in digital learning videos for secondary education?

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative content analysis approach to examine language use and cultural representation in digital learning videos designed for secondary education. Qualitative content analysis is particularly appropriate for studies that seek to interpret meaning-making patterns, discursive structures, and representational tendencies within media texts rather than to measure frequency alone (Schreier, 2012; Krippendorff, 2018). The research is grounded in media and cultural studies traditions, which treat educational videos not merely as pedagogical tools but as cultural texts that encode particular assumptions about learners, knowledge, language, and identity. An exploratory design is particularly suitable for this study because the objective is not to measure instructional effectiveness or learner outcomes, but to map representational patterns and tendencies across platforms operating at different governance levels. The analysis therefore prioritises interpretive depth over statistical generalisation. In line with media and cultural studies traditions, the selected videos are treated as institutionally situated cultural artefacts that encode assumptions about learners, knowledge, and pedagogy operating at three distinct levels of governance:

1. State Level: Digital learning videos produced under the *Banglar Shiksha Online* initiative of the School Education Department, Government of West Bengal where the videos are primarily designed for students following the West Bengal Board of Secondary Education curriculum and are predominantly delivered in the Bengali language.
2. National Level: Video content produced or endorsed by the NCERT and disseminated through national platforms such as DIKSHA and PM eVidya where the videos are intended

for a pan Indian audience and reflect centrally standardised curricular and pedagogical frameworks.

3. Global Level: Educational videos produced by Khan Academy, a global non-profit organisation offering free instructional content across disciplines where the videos are designed for a global audience and are primarily delivered in English.

The research universe comprises publicly accessible, video-based digital learning resources created for secondary school students (Grades IX–X) and disseminated through online platforms as for lower classes there are very low videos available. Together, these three categories represent distinct institutional, linguistic, and cultural orientations in digital education, allowing for a comparative overview of representational practices.

Sampling

The study employs purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique commonly used in qualitative media research to select information rich cases that are most relevant to the research objectives to identify information-rich cases that illuminate the phenomenon under investigation (Patton, 2015; Palinkas et al., 2015). Purposive sampling is particularly appropriate in media analysis where the objective is analytical depth rather than statistical generalisation (Krippendorff, 2018). Consistent with similar qualitative studies of educational media and digital learning environments, videos were selected based on their relevance to the research questions, accessibility, and representativeness of typical instructional formats within each platform. The purpose of comparison is therefore not to establish equivalence between platforms but to examine how representational logics systematically shift with governance scale. The sample size is consistent with qualitative media studies that prioritise depth of interpretation over numerical representativeness.

A total of ten videos were selected (state = 4; national = 3; global = 3). The videos range approximately between 10 and 55 minutes in duration. The sample size was deliberately kept small to enable close, interpretive analysis, which is consistent with qualitative media research designs (Schreier, 2012). Videos were included using the following criteria: (i) *targeted secondary-level curriculum (Grades IX–X)*, (ii) *publicly accessible without institutional login*, (iii) *officially produced or disseminated by the respective platform*, (iv) *representation of both STEM and non-STEM subjects*, (v) *typical instructional structure for the platform*.

The individual instructional video constitutes the primary unit of analysis. Each video was analysed in its entirety as a coherent media text, with attention to both verbal and visual

elements where within each video, the components that were examined are spoken narration and instructional language, visual design and classroom representation. Examples, metaphors, and cultural references alongside pedagogical cues and implied learner engagement were also observed. Importantly, the comparison across governance levels is not intended to evaluate platform effectiveness but to examine how representational logics shift with institutional scale, particularly in relation to language, cultural contextualisation, and learner positioning.

Rather than relying on predefined quantitative indicators, the framework allows for interpretive coding of patterns related to language, culture, and learner positioning. The analysis draws on an integrated qualitative framework combining Representation theory, which conceptualises media as sites where meaning, identity, and ideology are constructed (Hall, 1997), critical media pedagogy, which recognises educational media as socially situated practices, and also visual and narrative content analysis, focusing on how meaning is conveyed through images, animations, and instructional structure.

Coding

A thematic coding scheme was developed through a two-stage process, deductive coding and inductive coding. In stage one, for deductive coding, initial coding categories were derived from existing literature on educational media, representation, and language in instruction which included language of instruction, cultural references and localisation, representation of learner identity, classroom environment, and governance orientation. Deductive coding is appropriate when categories are derived from established conceptual frameworks and prior research (Schreier, 2012). Initial coding categories were derived from existing scholarship on media representation (Hall, 1997), critical media pedagogy (Buckingham, 2003; Selwyn, 2016), localisation and language in digital content (Esselink, 2000; Chowdhury et al., 2011), and discourse and learner positioning (Fairclough, 1995; van Dijk, 1993). For stage two, inductive refinement, during repeated viewing of the videos, additional sub themes were identified and incorporated into the coding framework, such as degree of abstraction versus contextualisation, visual hierarchy and authority cues, nature of interactivity and feedback, and use of animation and multimedia.

These categories reflect dimensions widely discussed in studies of educational media and digital pedagogy (Buckingham, 2003; Selwyn, 2016; Krippendorff, 2018). Each video was viewed multiple times to ensure consistency and accuracy in coding, and analytical notes were recorded systematically for each category. The coding of each video analysed for this study included the following parameters: (i) Language of instruction: medium, register, and

accessibility; (ii) Cultural specificity: presence or absence of regional, national, or global references; (iii) Classroom representation: physical, virtual, or abstract learning environment; (iv) Instructional materials: use of boards, textbooks, diagrams, animations; (v) Learner identity construction: assumptions about learner background and agency; (vi) Interaction and feedback: rhetorical engagement, exercises, platform based interaction; (vii) Assignments and supplementary resources: references to tasks, worksheets, or external materials; (viii) Use of animation and multimedia: extent and pedagogical function; (ix) Localisation: adaptation to linguistic and cultural contexts; (x) Governance orientation: institutional priorities shaping content design.

Data Interpretation

Data interpretation focused on identifying recurring representational patterns rather than isolated instances and to enhance analytical validity the findings were interpreted comparatively across governance levels, interpretations were grounded in explicit textual and visual evidence from the videos, and claims were framed as tendencies and orientations, not universal generalisations. The study does not claim representativeness of all digital learning videos; instead, it offers a contextualised overview of how representation operates within selected influential platforms and all analysed materials are publicly available educational videos. No human participants were involved, and no personal data were collected. The study hence therefore did not require institutional ethical clearance.

The study however acknowledges certain limitations like it has a small, purposive sample that limits generalisability, and analysis that is confined to video content, excluding learner reception or engagement data. Also platform level interactivity (e.g., analytics, adaptive learning) is considered only where explicitly linked to the video and these limitations are consistent with the exploratory scope of the research. The analysis prioritised pattern identification across governance levels rather than frequency counts, consistent with qualitative content analysis approaches (Schreier, 2012).

Analysis and Findings

This section presents a comparative content analysis of state level, national level, and global digital learning videos, focusing on how language, culture, learner identity, pedagogy, and governance are represented and encoded within instructional media and rather than evaluating effectiveness, the analysis foregrounds representation as a cultural and institutional practice embedded in educational media.

Language as Pedagogical Access and Symbolic Power

Language emerges as a foundational axis of representation across all three governance levels, functioning simultaneously as a tool of instruction and a marker of legitimacy and authority. Across platforms, language functions as a mechanism of inclusion and exclusion, shaping who can fully participate in digital classrooms and as governance scale increases, linguistic diversity decreases, reinforcing dominant language ideologies. The *Banglar Shiksha* videos consistently employ Bengali as the exclusive medium of instruction, including for STEM subjects such as life science and physical science where technical concepts are translated into Bengali using explanatory paraphrasing rather than English, affirming the epistemic legitimacy of this regional language in conveying scientific and literary knowledge. Further, for the non STEM subjects too such as Bengali literature, where linguistic representation is deeply embedded within cultural identity. With literary analysis conducted entirely in standard Bengali registering even in English literature lessons, the former remains a dominant explanatory language. While English texts mediated through translation and cultural contexts for understanding. Whereas at national level, instructional language naturally shifts toward English and Hindi, as is convenient for different kinds of national learners, privileging English in STEM content type. While the educational videos aim for clarity and inclusivity, the linguistic factor is registering as standardised and institutional, assuming functional bilingualism; creating a linguistic hierarchy where regional languages are absent, and all types of comprehension is dependent on prior exposure. Khan Academy videos, a global platform, employs a conversational tone in English masking the underlying linguistic gatekeeping, making fluency of this language a prerequisite, thereby, naturalising linguistic privilege under the typical guise of global accessibility.

Cultural Context, Local Knowledge, and Representational Depth

It is witnessed that cultural representation varies across different governance levels revealing difficulty in maintaining cultural neutrality in educational media. This reflects a design ideology that prioritises scalability over cultural belonging, often at the expense of learners from marginalised contexts. *Banglar Shiksha* videos demonstrate high cultural situatedness, particularly in humanities content. Bengali literature lessons explicitly reference regional history, idioms, and aesthetic traditions. Even STEM lessons occasionally draw on locally familiar experiences such as household examples or regionally recognisable flora and fauna to anchor abstract concepts, but however, cultural representation within the state frame tends to be internally homogenised, privileging urban, standard Bengali culture while marginalising

intra regional diversity. DIKSHA videos adopt a pan Indian cultural neutrality, using examples that are nationally recognisable but losing their cultural nuances. The lessons in Geography lessons with reference to Indian wetlands and conservation efforts are stripped of local specificity and socio-cultural depth and this approach produces a decontextualised Indian learner, where diversity is acknowledged symbolically but not substantively represented. Khan Academy videos are deliberately culture agnostic, using abstract metaphors, diagrams, and universally framed examples and this abstraction facilitates global scalability but eliminates any engagement with learners' lived realities.

Imagined Classroom and Pedagogical Authority

The “classroom” portrayed itself differs across platforms, signaling distinct pedagogical ideologies, where representation at state level videos tends to replicate the physical classroom, featuring a teacher, blackboard, and textbook centred instruction where authority resides visibly with the teacher as a state sanctioned knowledge bearer; with typical branding of the government initiative. Whereas, national level videos construct a mediated institutional classroom, blending teacher presence with digital slides and animations, and the global level videos tends to dissolve the classroom entirely, replacing it with a personalised digital interface where learning appears self-directed and asynchronous, and hence these representations reflect a shift from collective, institutionally grounded learning to individualised platform based pedagogy, with implications for learner accountability and socialisation.

Learner Identity and Subject Positioning

Each platform encodes a distinct imagined learner identity where learner diversity across class, gender, ability, and language is largely implicit rather than explicitly acknowledged across all platforms. *Banglar Shiksha* constructs the learner as a regionally rooted, examination-oriented student, embedded within state curricula and linguistic culture. On the otherhand, DIKSHA imagines a standardised national learner, adaptable and mobile but culturally neutral, and Khan Academy positions the learner as a globally mobile, autonomous individual, detached from institutional schooling structures.

Interaction, Assessment, and Pedagogical Closure

Across all videos, interaction remains largely one directional, though framed differently where this distinction highlights a move from broadcast pedagogy to data driven learning architectures, where learner engagement is tracked beyond the video. State and national videos

rely on rhetorical questioning and textbook references, whereas Khan Academy shifts interactivity outside the video, embedding assessment and feedback within the platform ecosystem rather than the audiovisual text itself.

Table 1: Comparison table showing various parameters of state, national and global level digital learning videos

Parameter	State Level (<i>Banglar Shiksha</i>)	National Level (DIKSHA)	Global Level (Khan Academy)
Language of Instruction	Bengali	English / Hindi	English
Cultural Context	Region-specific	Pan-Indian, neutral	Culturally abstract
Classroom Representation	Physical classroom	Studio / virtual classroom	Digital whiteboard
Learner Identity	Regional, exam-oriented	Standardised national learner	Autonomous global learner
Pedagogical Mode	Lecture + board work	Slides + animation	Animated explanations
Interaction	Rhetorical prompts	Rhetorical + references	Platform-based (external)
Localisation	High	Moderate	Low
Governance Orientation	State curriculum	National standardisation	Global scalability

Animation, Visual Design, and Knowledge Abstraction

The use of animation intensifies with governance scale, while animations enhance conceptual clarity, they also promote visual standardisation, reducing opportunities for cultural specificity. Minimal animation in state level videos, prioritising live instruction and board work, in contrast, there is moderate, explanatory animation in national videos, especially for abstract scientific concepts, and very significantly, extensive animated visualisation in Khan Academy, where diagrams and motion form the primary explanatory mode.

Table 2 : Comparison table showing various illustrative verbal evidence across platforms

Platform	Video Title	Time stamp (mm:ss)	Verbatim Example	Analytical Interpretation
State (Banglar Shiksha Online)	<i>Animal Movement (Life Science)</i>	00:42 – 00:55	“আজ আমরা প্রাণীর চলন সম্পর্কে আলোচনা করব”	Opening in Bengali signals strong linguistic localisation and alignment with regional classroom practice.
State (Banglar Shiksha Online)	<i>Father's Help (English)</i>	02:15 – 02:40	“এখন আমরা গল্পটা বুঝে নেব”	Continued reliance on Bengali mediation within an English lesson reinforces the pedagogical centrality of the regional language.
National (NCERT / DIKSHA)	<i>Management of Wetlands</i>	01:18 – 01:30	“In this lesson we will learn about the management of wetlands.”	Formal English register reflects standardised national framing with limited regional contextualisation.
Global (Khan Academy)	<i>Intro to the Pythagorean Theorem</i>	00:03 – 00:20	“Let's think about the Pythagorean theorem.”	Immediate shift to abstract mathematical explanation indicates a decontextualised, globally oriented pedagogical style.

(Note- Verbatim excerpts are reproduced from publicly available instructional videos and translated where necessary.)

Governance and Ideological Orientation

Governance structures profoundly shape representational choices where these priorities directly influence whose knowledge, language, and cultural context are foregrounded or marginalised. State platforms prioritise linguistic access and curricular alignment, national

platforms prioritise uniformity and policy coherence, and global platforms prioritise scalability, efficiency, and platform logic.

The table below presents selected verbatim excerpts with timestamps to substantiate the interpretive coding across platforms.

One can say that digital learning videos are culturally and institutionally encoded artefacts, not just neutral conveyors of knowledge; as educational content scales from regional to global platforms because it undergoes progressive de-contextualisation, demonstrates significant implications for representation, inclusion, and learner identity.

Discussion

Drawing together insights from theories and analysis of selected videos, the study focuses on how educational media do not merely transmit curricular knowledge but actively produce an imagined classroom and an imagined learner whose contours shift with governance scale, where one of the most striking findings is the graduated transformation of language from a marker of cultural belonging at the state level to a marker of global competence at the international level, and this trajectory closely mirrors Hall's (1997) conception of representation as a site where meaning and power are negotiated rather than neutrally conveyed.

At the state level, the use of Bengali across STEM and non-STEM subjects functions as a political and pedagogical affirmation of linguistic legitimacy. Rather than positioning English as the sole carrier of scientific or academic authority, *Banglar Shiksha* Online re anchors epistemic authority in the regional language as the finding resonates with scholarship on multilingual education, which demonstrates that mother tongue instruction enhances conceptual understanding and learner confidence, particularly in complex domains such as science (Chowdhury et al., 2011; Ministry of Education, 2020). At the national level, however, linguistic representation shifts toward standardisation, with English and Hindi dominating instructional discourse while this bilingual approach is designed to ensure national coherence, it also introduces a form of linguistic flattening, where regional languages become peripheral which aligns with Selwyn's (2016) critique of digital education platforms as sites where uniformity often supersedes inclusivity under the guise of scalability. Globally, the exclusive use of English on platforms such as Khan Academy further intensifies this dynamic as it is delivered in an accessible, conversational register, English operates here as an unmarked norm,

naturalising global linguistic hierarchies and implicitly privileging learners with prior English capital. As several scholars have argued, such neutral global discourse is rarely neutral in effect, particularly in postcolonial and multilingual contexts (Pym, 2010; Karimov et al., 2024).

A systematic process of progressive decontextualisation as digital learning videos scale from state to global platforms where state level content demonstrates high cultural embedded-ness. Further, in humanities subjects in particular examples, metaphors, and narratives are rooted in regional history and everyday life, as a form of situated pedagogy that fosters a sense of cultural familiarity and symbolic inclusion, reinforcing Buckingham's (2003) argument that learners engage more meaningfully with media that recognises their lived realities. National level videos adopt a strategy of cultural neutrality, using pan Indian examples that are broadly recognisable but rarely deeply contextualised, while this approach avoids overt regional bias, it also risks producing what Fairclough (1995) terms discursive abstraction, where social and cultural particularities are systematically erased in favour of institutional coherence. Global platforms take this abstraction to its logical extreme by deliberately removing cultural markers, as Khan Academy constructs a placeless pedagogical environment, where knowledge appears universally applicable and socially unanchored, although this enhances global portability (Bergstrom & Yamkovenko, 2025, March 20), it also raises critical questions about whose knowledge and experiences are rendered visible within such global classrooms; and as the literature on localisation cautions the decontextualised content often shifts to privileged cultural norms while marginalising learners who require cultural mediation to actually fully engage (Chowdhury et al., 2011; Esselink, 2000).

State level videos visually and narratively reproduce the traditional classroom, with the teacher occupying a central authoritative position and this continuity reinforces the legitimacy of formal schooling and situates learning within a collective institutional framework. National level platforms introduce a hybrid model, blending teacher authority with digital mediation where the classroom becomes a technologically augmented institutional space, reflecting the state's attempt to modernise without fully relinquishing pedagogical control. Global platforms, by contrast, dissolve the classroom altogether where learning is relocated to a personalised digital interface, where the teacher's authority is replaced by platform design and algorithmic sequencing and this transformation echoes Selwyn's (2016) critique of platformised education, wherein pedagogical authority shifts from educators to technology providers, subtly reshaping notions of responsibility, accountability, and learner agency.

Across governance levels, the construction of learner identity becomes increasingly individualised and abstracted. State level content imagines learners as regionally situated

students preparing for specific examinations. National platforms imagine a mobile, standardised learner adaptable to uniform curricular demands. Global platforms imagine a self-motivated, autonomous learner untethered from institutional or cultural constraints. While this progression may appear pedagogically progressive, it raises concerns about symbolic exclusion (Bergstrom & Yamkovenko, 2025, March 20). Learners who do not conform to the imagined profile if whether due to linguistic limitations, cultural distance, or infrastructural constraints, risk being positioned at the margins of the digital classroom. This finding aligns with existing research on digital divides, which emphasises that access is not merely technological but deeply cultural and symbolic (Selwyn, 2016; Azim Premji Foundation, 2021).

The study further reveals how interactivity is unevenly distributed across platforms. State and national videos rely primarily on rhetorical engagement, maintaining a broadcast pedagogical model while global platforms externalise interactivity to the platform ecosystem, embedding feedback, assessment, and progression tracking beyond the video text itself, while such data driven pedagogies offer advantages in personalisation, they also reframe learning as a quantifiable and scrutinised activity, raising ethical and pedagogical questions about data governance and learner autonomy and one can argue that platform centric models risk privileging measurable outcomes over culturally responsive learning processes (Selwyn, 2016; Murphy et al., 2014). Ultimately, the differences observed across platforms are not accidental but are shaped by governance priorities. State initiatives prioritise linguistic inclusion and curricular alignment while national platforms prefer standardisation and policy coherence. The global platforms prioritise scalability and efficiency. These priorities, in turn, shape representational choices that have tangible implications for social inclusion and educational equity.

This study thus reinforces the argument that educational media must be understood as an ideological artefact, embedded within broader political and institutional structures. This reflects Hall's (1997) notion of representation, that is always implicated in power. Hence, digital learning videos are no exception where inclusive digital education cannot be achieved through technological innovation alone. Rather, it requires intentional representational design, where language, culture, and learner diversity are foregrounded rather than treated as peripheral concerns. A multi-layered approach combining the linguistic accessibility of state platforms, the infrastructural reach of national systems, and the pedagogical innovations of global platforms, may offer a more equitable model for the future by situating digital learning videos within a comparative representational framework. This study contributes to the ongoing debates on media, education, and social justice, hence, demonstrating that the digital classroom

is not a neutral space but a contested site where language, culture, and power intersect, shaping how learners see themselves and their place within educational institutions and society at large.

This risk transforming education from a socially embedded practice into a technically optimised product, distancing knowledge from the communities it is meant to serve. The progressive abstraction of language and culture observed across governance levels, thus, signals not merely a pedagogical shift but a structural realignment in which educational authority migrates away from local public institutions toward centralised or platform-based systems. Such transformations invite critical reflection on whether digital education, in its current form, functions to democratise knowledge or to reorganise educational access along new, less visible lines of inequality.

Conclusion

After analysing various state, national, and global digital learning videos via the lens of language, culture, learner identity, and pedagogical design, this paper foregrounds that digital education using media is deeply implicated at a broader social, cultural, and political process where one of the central findings is that the scale profoundly shapes representation as educational media content moves from a regional to global platforms. There is a marked shift from linguistic to cultural specificity and is tending towards abstraction and standardisation for relevance. Regional level initiatives such as *Banglar Shiksha Online* focusing on West Bengal board of education foregrounds on regional language for curricular familiarity offering learners a sense of local cultural recognition. The national platforms though aim for inclusivity, catering to central board or other national boards of education with very less regional level inclusivity, often leaves ground of imbalance in policy coherence. This results in a eroding of regional and linguistic diversity in a more nationalistic approach. Global platforms like the Khan Academy, further intensifies by constructing a culturally de-contextualised learning space that assumes dominant English fluency and self-directed learning as a universal norms. This kind of progression raises important questions about whose knowledge and experiences are being legitimised within those classrooms or is a mere mechanistic transformation. While global platforms frequently celebrated for their amazing reach and technological sophistication, rely on abstract and culturally neutral narratives risking various marginalised learners who tend to believe that dominant linguistic mediation is required to fully engage with academic content. Hence, global scalability may inadvertently reproduce existing educational inequalities and also confuse learners rather than mitigate such issues.

Critically, the current discourse on online education particularly in policy and with growth of EdTech narratives, overemphasising or glamourising access and innovation while it is under examining representation, identity, and power. The study highlights on how these educational videos using media tends to reshape the idea of the classroom itself and is changing behaviours among learners, because traditional collective learning spaces that anchored in teacher student relationships are being gradually replaced by individualised, platform driven learning environments offering flexibility and autonomy. These platforms also displace pedagogical authority from educators to technological systems, thus, raising concerns about accountability, pedagogical depth, and the slow erosion of culturally responsive teaching practices. The assumption that this digital content is inherently inclusive, totally obscures the subtle ways in which governance priorities are embedded in educational media. Without deliberate attention to these dimensions, digital learning tends to risk becoming a new site of symbolic exclusion, even as it expands formal access, especially with new technologies.

This paper argues that representation matters in education as digital learning videos which uses media shapes not only what a student learns, but also, how an individual see themselves as a learner and a citizen of a country. This study does not wish to comment for a rejection of global or national digital platforms but rather it calls for a more diverse reflexive and plural approach to digital education design that integrates the strengths of different governance levels where inclusive linguistic accessibility and cultural situated-ness. As demonstrated by West Bengal state level initiative like many other state/regional level initiatives, educational video must be treated as foundational rather than supplementary. The national platforms should move beyond mere standardisation to actively support more meaningful localisation, and the global platforms, in turn, must engage more seriously with cultural diversity and the social contexts of learners in the global south. This makes learners more interested as well to know about their roots while growing up and identifying in plural societies. In Global south, countries such as India, the question is no longer confined to whether digital education will expand, but whose voices, languages, and cultures will be carried forward within it. Hence, addressing these questions are essential if digital education is to serve the goals of equity, inclusion, and social justice rather than simply reproducing existing hierarchies in some kind of a digital form.

Digital learning videos when shaped primarily just by imperatives of uniformity or global reach does risk undermining the local linguistic and cultural plurality that sustains educational equity in diverse societies. While technology can expand access, but access alone does not guarantee inclusion, hence, meaningful inclusion do require that learners see their languages, cultures, and social realities reflected within educational media. The patterns identified in this study

reaffirm the necessity of recognising education particularly in a secondary education setting as a collective social right rather than a just scalable technological solution and a socially just digital education ecosystem must therefore prioritise public accountability, cultural localisation, and pedagogical solidarity; to ensure technological innovation strengthening rather than displacing the emancipatory role of education within such diverse society.

While the selected videos are illustrative of broader platform tendencies, hence, they do not capture the full diversity of content available across state, national, and global educational platforms, this study is exploratory in scope and is subject to certain limitations. First, the analysis is based on a small, purposively selected sample of digital learning videos, which limits the generalisability of the findings. Further, the study focuses exclusively on content level representation and does not examine learner reception, engagement, or learning outcomes. At the end the analysis is limited to video-based instructional content and does not consider other digital affordances such as discussion forums, adaptive algorithms, or platform analytics, which may further shape learner experience. As such, one may say that it cannot account for how students from different socio-cultural backgrounds interpret or negotiate these representations in practice.

Future studies could explore broader sample sizes including comparative studies across multiple states or linguistic regions to examine intra national variation in representation. Studies may incorporate student and teacher perspectives which would provide valuable insights into how digital representations are received and mediated within classrooms and can also include a fresh perspective of current parent-teacher-student relationship. Additionally, various longitudinal research could explore how sustained exposure to globalised educational media influences learner identity, language attitudes, and educational aspirations and this type of research would deepen understanding of the cultural and social implications of digital education to inform the development of more inclusive and context sensitive digital learning ecosystems.

References

Apple, M. W. (2004). *Ideology and curriculum* (3rd ed.). New York, NY: Routledge.

Azim Premji Foundation. (2021). *Loss of learning during the pandemic*. Azim Premji Foundation.

<https://cdn.azimpremjiuniversity.edu.in/media/publications/downloads/report/Learning-Loss-during-pandemicc.f1712062129.pdf>

- Banglar Shiksha Online. (2020, April 20). *Class X life science: Animal movement (Part 1)* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U6mgVAa5qmg>
- Banglar Shiksha Online. (2020, May 5). *Class X English: Father's help (Bliss)* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wTkvfMVSAO4>
- Bergstrom, A. & Yamkovenko, B. (2025, March 20). University of Toronto Randomized Controlled Trial of 11K Students Demonstrates a Meaningful, Positive Effect of Khan Academy on Student Learning. *Khan Academy Blog*. <https://blog.khanacademy.org/university-of-toronto-randomized-controlled-trial-of-11k-students-demonstrates-a-meaningful-positive-effect-of-khan-academy-on-student-learning/>
- Buckingham, D. (2003). *Media education: Literacy, learning and contemporary culture*. Polity Press.
- Chitra, K.R. & Senthilkumar, N. (2023). Gender representations and portrayal of adults in children's television advertising: content analysis of prime cartoon channels in India. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1234678>
- Chowdhury, M. D., Al-Mahmood, A., Bashar, M. A., & Ahmed, J. U. (2011). Localization of Digital Content for Use in Secondary Schools of Bangladesh. ERIC Document ED523765). ERIC. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED523765.pdf>
- de Moura Caria, L., et al. (2017). *Impact of Khan Academy in Brazilian public schools: Randomized evaluation findings* (Lemann Foundation / J-PAL partnership report). <https://www.povertyactionlab.org/evaluation/impact-online-math-learning-platform-test-scores-and-attitudes-towards-math-brazil>
- Esselink, B. (2000). *A practical guide to localization*. John Benjamins.
- Fairclough, N. (1995). *Media discourse*. Edward Arnold.
- Giroux, H. A. (2011). *On critical pedagogy*. Bloomsbury.
- Hall, S. (1997). *Representation: Cultural representations and signifying practices* (2nd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Karimov A, Nolte A, Chounta I-A, Saarela M and Kärkkäinen T (2025) Improving learning experience through process re-engineering: Khan Academy localization into Azerbaijani. *Frontiers in Education*. 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2024.1419362>
- Karwal, A. (2021). DIKSHA - Learnings from India Experience. Department of School Education and Literacy, *Ministry of Education, Government of India*. https://diksha.gov.in/assets/download/Secretary_DoSEL_Presentation_World_Bank_Webinar.pdf
- Krippendorff, K. (2018). *Content analysis: An introduction to its methodology* (4th ed.). SAGE.
- Khan Academy. (2018). *Intro to the Pythagorean theorem* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JVrkLlCA2qw>

- Ministry of Education, Government of India. (2020). *National Education Policy 2020*. Government of India.
https://static.pib.gov.in/WriteReadData/userfiles/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf
- Murphy, R., Gallagher, L., Krumm, A. E., Mislavy, J., & Hafter, A. (2014). Research on the use of Khan Academy in schools: *Implementation report*. SRI International.
<https://www.sri.com/publication/education-learning-pubs/digital-learning-pubs/research-on-the-use-of-khan-academy-in-schools-implementation-report/>
- National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT). (2021). *Management of wetlands (Part 1)* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=srsWv-UwJz0>
- OECD. (2020, March 20). *Education responses to COVID-19: Embracing digital learning and online collaboration*. OECD Policy Responses to Coronavirus (COVID-19), Paris: OECD Publishing, <https://doi.org/10.1787/d75eb0e8-en>
- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), 533–544. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y>
- Patton, M. Q. (2015). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods* (4th ed.). SAGE.
- Pym, A. (2010). *Exploring translation theories*. Routledge.
- Schreier, M. (2012). *Qualitative content analysis in practice*. SAGE.
- Selwyn, N. (2016). *Education and technology: Key issues and debates*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Sharma, A. (2021). *Guide for DIKSHA implementation in schools: Learnings from India experience* (ICT India Working Paper). Columbia University / CSD working paper.
https://csd.columbia.edu/sites/default/files/content/docs/ICT%20India/Papers/ICT_India_Working_Paper_50.pdf
- UNESCO. (2017). *Accountability in education: Meeting our commitments*. UNESCO Digital Library. <https://doi.org/10.54676/VVRO7638>
- van Dijk, T. A. (1993). Principles of critical discourse analysis. *Discourse & Society*, 4(2), 249–283. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0957926593004002006>
- Williamson, B., & Hogan, A. (2020). *Commercialisation and privatisation in/of education in the context of COVID-19*. Education International.
- Yadav, R. (2024). Gender and media: A critical review of representation and impacts. *International Journal of Applied Social Science*, 10(11-12), 778–787.
<https://scientificresearchjournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/social-science-vol-10-778-787.pdf>